

Triangle - p1

Database

Not shared: draw a card
Max 1 article/researcher

Shared: max 2 articles
per researcher

Fame: 3

Database

Not shared: draw a card
Max 1 article/researcher

Shared: max 2 articles
per researcher

Fame: 3

Database

Not shared: draw a card
Max 1 article/researcher

FALSE

If Review: -6 Fame for you
-2 Fame for each article

Fame: 3

Experiment

Not shared: draw a card
Max 1 article/researcher

Shared: max 2 articles
per researcher

Fame: 2

Experiment

Not shared: draw a card
Max 1 article/researcher

Shared: max 2 articles
per researcher

Fame: 2

Experiment

Not shared: draw a card
Max 1 article/researcher

FALSE

If Review: -4 Fame for you
-2 Fame for each article

Fame: 2

Code

Not shared: draw a card
Max 1 article/researcher

Shared: max 2 articles
per researcher

Fame: 1

Code

Not shared: draw a card
Max 1 article/researcher

Shared: max 2 articles
per researcher

Fame: 1

Code

Not shared: draw a card
Max 1 article/researcher

FALSE

If Review: -2 Fame for you
-1 Fame for each article

Fame: 1

